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GEOMETRIC DIGITAL TWIN FOR CONSERVATION PROJECT: THE CASE OF THE ST. BASIL OF OSTROG CHURCH IN NIKŠIĆ (MONTENEGRO)

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ABSTRACT

Creating a conservation project for culturally significant buildings is a complex process that requires good and thorough documentation. The documentation covers various data types that require analysis to solve different heritage problems and obtain accurate data for restoration works. In the case of the St. Basil of Ostrog church in Nikšić, Montenegro, a geometric digital twin (gDT) was created using laser scanning and photogrammetry to provide geometry accuracy and descriptive data of the building fabric. Since its construction, the original architectural drawings from the late 19th century have not been preserved and there is a lack of proper documentation. The Cathedral Church, built in the Byzantine style, is a complex structure consisting of interlinked objects. It has started to show signs of various pathologies that need to be addressed. The photorealistic geometric digital twin has been shown as an effective tool for obtaining accurate and descriptive information in the case of intricate heritage buildings. To obtain gDT, different technologies have been used such as laser scanning and areal and close-range photogrammetry. This paper aims to demonstrate how different kinds of digital data (historical, geometric, pathological, and performance) benefit from a geometric digital twin to create a conservation project and continue to monitor this Montenegrin heritage building closely. The conservation project of the St. Basil of Ostrog church in Nikšić was created according to the Conservation conditions issued by the Cultural Heritage Protection Administration of Montenegro, which defines what needs to be achieved by the project to improve the condition of the heritage building.

KEYWORDS: preventive approach, digitisation, cultural heritage, church, digital data, geometry, pathology, laser scanning, photogrammetry, conservation.

1. INTRODUCTION

A shift from a curative to a preventive conservation approach to safeguard the cultural significance and authentic essence of heritage assets steadily becoming imperative in the conservation practice. This shift aims to reduce the necessity for later interventions and associated costs, ultimately preserving cultural heritage more effectively (Masciotta et al., 2019). The preventive conservation approach advocates for proactive measures, such as early detection and a comprehensive understanding of the deterioration process through consistent on-site monitoring and maintenance activities. Preventive conservation aims

to minimise future losses, placing a crucial emphasis on anticipating what lies ahead. Preventive conservators employ strategies like risk management and collection condition surveys to assess past conditions, identify current risks, and effectively prepare for what the future may hold (Masciotta et al., 2019; Henderson 2018; Psalti et al., 2022; Kucak 2022).

In the case of the church of St. Basil of Ostrog, which was built between 1895-1899 in the center of Nikšić (Figure 1) and is included as an immovable cultural monument, the method of preventive conservation is based on the preparation of the geometrical digital twin - gDT.

Figure 1. a) Map of the region and location of the church (Source: <https://sr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nikšić>); b) Satellite map of Nikšić city and location of the church (Source: <https://geoportal.co.me/Geoportal01/>)

This paper aims to determine the possibilities of the data obtained from analysing the gDT of the Saint Basil of Ostrog church for conservation purposes. Almost no research has been done on this church until now, which is why this work provides new information about its current state of preservation and its history. The study is based on in situ reconnaissance of the church, analysis of geometry, pathology and moisture, and comparative study of anomalies obtained with a realistic geometric digital twin using laser scanning and photogrammetry.

The paper has four main contributions. Firstly, it investigates and applies state-of-the-art practices and methods in researching the generation and maintenance of geometrical digital twins (gDTs). Secondly, it demonstrates creating a geometry-based (gDT) model of Saint Basil of Ostrog Church in Nikšić. Thirdly, it presents the integration of the gDT model into conservation practice through the context of digital documentation. Fourth, it demonstrates the importance of the preventive approach amplifying certain aspects over the curative approach.

In the first stage, the study deals with current technologies and methods for obtaining gDT emphasizing laser scanning technology and photogrammetry to achieve the most descriptive and accurate gDTs of the Saint Basil of Ostrog church. Physical characteristics (dimensions) of the church, its geometry and materials defined the most appropriate method to achieve an accurate gDT. Additionally, it demonstrates the importance of digital documentation of heritage buildings in different phases of conservation projects. The paper deals with the common conservation practice in Montenegro, accompanied by the historical data of the church. The second stage demonstrates the acquisition and modelling gDT of the church. The third stage presents that obtaining precise measurements using these techniques has also made it possible to establish the material and some of the structural pathologies as well as to deal with the problem of moisture.

The novelty of this study is based on the idea that a geometric digital twin can provide reliable and accurate data in various stages of a preventive conservation project, such as determining material pathologies and geometric structural deformations, as well as

mapping water intrusion and the appearance of moisture on heritage buildings.

2. FRAMEWORK

2.1. Digitisation of cultural heritage buildings

Heritage documentation is defined as the systematic collection and archiving of material and immaterial elements of historical structures and the environment, which would provide accurate information that will enable proper preservation, monitoring and maintenance of such structures (Dore and Murphy 2017).

Proper documentation of heritage buildings is crucial for conservation practice, and fortunately, advanced technologies can provide accurate and dependable information. However, to ensure the success of the documentation process and meet its objectives, it is important to plan carefully and consider all aspects of the process. These technologies are capable of collecting targeted data that can be useful in various aspects of a heritage building and its necessary interventions. The digital transition first benefited the survey and documentation process. This paper integrates a framework of heritage building digital data (Figure 1) that includes a compilation of different types of data tailored to specific purposes, including historical, geometric, pathological and performance data, that form a comprehensive building documentation (Khalil, et al., 2021).

The documentation of cultural heritage buildings is now digitised in the form of a digital twin, containing a broad range of information (Drobnyi et al., 2023b; Noronha Pinto De Oliveira E Sousa and Correa 2023). A recent trend is to create a digital replica of the building linked to Industry 4.0. The creation of a digital twin requires thorough research and accurate documentation to accommodate necessary and updated building data for performance analysis (Khalil, et al., 2021; Kineber et al., 2023; Singh et al., 2021; Angjeliu et al., 2020; Jouan and Hallot, 2019).

This paper provides an overview of the methods implemented for constructing and maintaining the geometry of a digital twin of the St. Basil of Ostrog church in Nikšić. A church is a structure consisting of connected object instances, such as walls, roofs, arches, domes, tambour, beams, columns, staircases, cornices, windows, and doors, as well as electrical systems. Geometry is the study of three-dimensional (3D) objects and their relationships (Drobnyi et al.,

2023). In the construction industry, a Digital Twin (DT) is a repository of product and process information that stores and shares physical and functional properties of a building with various stakeholders (AECOs) throughout its lifecycle. As-is geometric digital twins (gDTs) refer to the process of generating building geometry for existing buildings during their operation stage without prior building geometry information from point cloud datasets (Drobnyi et al., 2023; Jouan and Hallot, 2019).

Based on the Categorisation of building data in the digital documentation of heritage buildings (Khalil et al., 2021), the study follows the classification of documentation and the needs of the AEC industry to create a conservation project (Figure 2).

The creation of gDT is based on digitising heritage buildings which involves two primary data acquisition techniques - photogrammetry and laser scanning. Both techniques can gather data from aerial or terrestrial platforms (Khalil and Stravoravdis, 2019).

Terrestrial laser scanning on a stationary tripod is the optimal method, offering unparalleled accuracy at the millimeter level. The technique is widely favored due to its reliability and the ability to integrate color information from images into the point cloud. One of the major drawbacks of using terrestrial laser scanning is the amount of time and effort required to complete the scanning process. This issue is particularly evident when dealing with large and intricate buildings such as the church of Saint Basil of Ostrog (cca length of 33 m, a width of 23 m, and a height of 34 m). Due to the need for complete coverage, a considerable number of scans must be conducted, which significantly slows down the entire process and makes it laborious (Khalil and Stravoravdis 2019.; Vuoto et al., 2023; Masciotta et al., 2023).

Photogrammetry for documenting buildings can be divided into two categories - aerial photogrammetry using unmanned aerial systems and close-range photogrammetry for documenting facades and interiors using a hand-held camera. Advancements in Structure from Motion and dense matching techniques have made the photogrammetric processing of acquired images much more automated, allowing for the generation of 3D reconstructions of buildings. However, this process is time-consuming and requires human intervention. Terrestrial laser scanning is the preferred choice over photogrammetry for applications requiring high accuracy (Khalil and Stravoravdis 2019; Vuoto et al., 2023).

Figure 2. Categorisation of the documentation data of heritage buildings in the case of the Saint Basil of Ostrog church

A digital twin is a virtual representation of an object or system designed to reflect a physical object accurately. As a tool, it provides data about heritage buildings to different stakeholders. These stakeholders have specific interests in various data types, representing a comprehensive structure of documentation. Geometry data is important for recording and visualizing the building's current fabric, which is particularly essential for architects, structural engineers, and the construction sector. Pathology data aims to

identify decay or damage over time, with a primary focus on the conservation industry, while performance data caters for analyses the building's operability (Khalil et al., 2021; Kineber et al., 2023; Oostwegel et al., 2022).

The goals were focused on geometry, pathology and moisture, as defined by the task and funding. During the creation of gDT (Figure 3), accurate records, surveys, shapes and characteristics of the church's fabric in its current state were aimed.

Figure 3. Photorealistic gDT of the Saint Basil of Ostrog church in Nikšić (Source: www.3dvirtualheritage.me)

2.2. Conservation project

According to common conservation practice in Montenegro, a conservation project is created prior to

the execution of restoration work for all protected cultural assets listed in the state register of cultural heritage assets of Montenegro. This type of project aims to describe the history of the object, clarify its histori-

cal development, outline the current state of the object, define problematic points, and present methods for their resolution. The conservation project is a multifaceted document, delving into the comprehension of the object, evaluating the heritage's significance, and inspecting its internal elements (Oostwegel et al., 2022). The method of creation and the content of this project are legally regulated by the Law on the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Montenegro ("Zakon o zaštiti kulturnih dobara," n.d.), specifically by the Regulation outlining the detailed content of the conservation project for the implementation of conservation measures on cultural heritage ("Pravilnik o bližem sadržaju konzervatorskog projekta za sprovođenje konzervatorskih mjera na kulturnom dobru," n.d.). The Law on the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Montenegro defines the duties of the conservators, including research oversight and restoration interventions in heritage, advising owners on protection procedures, participation in the preparation of cultural protection conditions and consents for interventions on immovable heritage and preparation of management plans ("Zakon o zaštiti kulturnih dobara," n.d.).

A conservation project usually includes helpful visuals like images and 2D floor plans, coupled with in-depth descriptions of significant or vulnerable elements. This plan is neatly organized into three sections - a foundational document explaining the conservation process, a tailored document, known as the heritage survey, designed for more complex heritage situations, and a detailed document focusing on the practical steps for carrying out the conservation or restoration project, especially when significant modifications are needed (Oostwegel et al., 2022).

Conservation conditions require a project to conduct a detailed analysis of the current state of the building. All damages to the structure and materials need to be documented and presented graphically and textually through project documentation.

The development of the conservation project for the St. Basil of Ostrog church in Nikšić, was initiated by the Eparchy of Budimlja-Nikšić, the investor and the user of this church. The need to create a conservation project emerged while dampness penetrated the building extensively. For this reason, the main subject of the conservation project was the revision of the roof covering and roof structure. Additionally, the project encompassed the restoration of the facade, wooden carpentry, access stairs, and a part of the ground floor around the building. The main goal of this conservation project was to identify the points of dampness infiltration into the building, especially from the roof, to foresee appropriate measures to prevent this issue.

Taking into account all the specified requirements, the determination was that the most suitable approach for performing these analyses involves creating a gDT to comprehensively examine each segment of the building.

2.3. *The St. Basil of Ostrog church in Nikšić*

The Saint Basil of Ostrog church in Nikšić was built by Prince Nikola Petrović in honor and commemoration of fallen fighters in wars for liberation from the Turks during the period between 1875 and 1880. Financial assistance for the construction of the Church was provided by the Russian Synod and Tsar Nicholas II Romanov. The location for the construction of this magnificent church was determined by a commission at the suggestion of engineer Josip Slade. He chose a dominant position in the city, Peter's Hill, which was 16 meters high, to make the Church stand out in the urban setting. The church project, presented in 1892, was designed by the Russian architect Mikhail Timofeyevich Preobrazhensky (Mihail Timofijevič Preobraženski). The construction of the church took five years, with the foundation stone being laid in 1895 and the building completed in 1899 (Jokić, 2010).

Preobrazhensky designed the Cathedral Church following the Byzantine style, with a cross-in-square plan and a dome at the intersection of the main nave's vaults. The apse is externally three-sided and internally arched, connected to the prothesis and the diaconicon of lower height, as well as the side aisles. The front facade is emphasized by a belfry on the narthex. The primary construction material was hewn stone sourced from nearby quarries. The stone was expertly carved by skilled craftsmen, both local and from the surrounding region. The church's outer appearance is imposing and well-balanced, showcasing an elaborate design in its cornices, roof edges, arched entrances, and ornate stone sculptures on the façade (Jokić, 2010).

2.4. *Current state*

This cultural asset indicates a lack of regular maintenance and insufficient investment in the building over previous years. The facade surfaces and ornaments are visibly soiled from exhaust fumes, biological contaminants, and continuous water runoff along the facade. Also, all the facade stones have acquired a patina but are generally in good condition. Small and larger cracks are noticeable on the stone ornaments on the facades, on the frieze, cornices, and individual stone blocks, some of which have been improperly sealed in certain places. The junctions of the roof covering and the facade represent potential points of water penetration into the building, which causes the occurrence of mold inside the building. At

these junctions, there are unprofessional attempts to prevent moisture penetration, with multiple coatings that serve no purpose. The gutters are in extremely poor condition, dislocated from their beddings and severely damaged due to the large amount of atmospheric water. All the facade wooden carpentry is deteriorated and damaged by the effects of the sun and dampness (Figure 4). Window frames have dried out, locks and fittings are rusted or broken, and some parts have fallen off over time. All mentioned analyses need to be conducted to determine precise

measures for the restoration of the building (Cultural Heritage Protection Administration of Montenegro 2022).

The church's entrance doors are in somewhat better condition than the windows, but the influence of dampness is evident in the lower part of the door. The access staircase with retaining walls is overgrown with low and medium vegetation. The stone blocks of the staircase are partially dislocated and cracked in some places (AVM Architects LLC, 2023).

Figure 4. a) Interior mold and water penetration (Photo credit: Ražnatović, N.); b) Unprofessional attempt to seal junctions (Source: gDT model, Paten Studio LLC Podgorica); c) Detail of damaged gutters (Source: gDT model, Paten Studio LLC Podgorica); d) Detail of damaged wood carpentry (Photo credit: Ražnatović, N.).

3. DIGITISATION

3.1. Methodology

The primary objective behind constructing and maintaining gDT is to obtain detailed information about a building's geometry and fabrics. This information can be used to streamline the (1) planning, (2) restoration, and (3) maintenance processes, ultimately

resulting in a preventive conservation approach. The construction of gDTs is aimed at addressing this issue by providing digital product information for the Saint Basil of Ostrog church that lack such representation. This is particularly problematic for old buildings, like the church of St. Basil of Ostrog which as-designed product information lacks even in two-dimensional (2D) drawings that are prone to inaccuracies and become outdated over time.

Figure 5. 3D laser scanning point cloud of the church with its surroundings (Source: Paten Studio LLC Podgorica).

3.2. Digitisation of the church St. Basil of Ostrog in Nikšić

Various techniques have been used to capture and represent the geometry of the church of St. Basil of Ostrog in Nikšić, with different levels of accuracy,

cost efficiency, and time consumption. These methods range from areal and close-range photogrammetry (Khalil and Stravoravdis, 2019) to laser scanning. The FARO FocusM 70 Laser Scanner (Phase shift scanner) was used to obtain 360 HDR images of the church. Phase shift scanners determine distances by

analyzing the phase shift between continuously emitted and received laser beams. They offer a wide field of view, a high density of dots, and fast shutter speeds. These scanners are well-suited for high-precision and detailed measurements. The main advantage of the laser scanning technique is the direct production of point clouds (Figure 6) that define the object or scene (Ulvi 2021). Laser scan data was registered, processed and analysed in Faro Focus TLS-specific Scene software, including the cloud-to-cloud orientation method, for all 148 scans (Figure 5). The Repetition Nearest Points (RNP) algorithm was used to improve the alignment.

Photogrammetry is a technology that enables the acquisition of accurate measurements and three-dimensional data from photographs. Photogrammetry involves determining the position and shape of objects using photographs taken from different angles. It calculates 3D coordinates of object points based on overlapping images and known camera positions and orientations. Internal orientation parameters must be known, and external parameters can be calculated with at least three control points in overlapping images. The 3D coordinates are determined using equiv-

alent linearity equations relating object and image coordinates (Ulvi 2021; Huesca-Tortosa, Spairani-Berrio, and Saura-Gómez 2023). It includes two types, areal photogrammetry and close-range photogrammetry, which share the same key principle of triangulation.

Both digital images captured with photogrammetric techniques and TLS itself can be processed using specific software (Reality Capture) to obtain point clouds with their true colors. The photos were taken with Mavic 2 Pro with sensor 1" CMOS, effective pixels of 20 million and lens FOV: about 77°, 35 mm Format Equivalent: 28 mm, aperture: f/2.8-f/11, Shooting range: 1 m to ∞ and a Canon EOS 250D DSLR camera with 24,1 MP – APS-C sensor, image processing engine DIGIC 8 with an ISO sensitivity range of 100–25600.

Due to the tall vegetation surrounding the church, a preliminary study for planning the implementation and positioning of the apparatus defined the positions and number of scans, as well as the analysis of the accessibility of the surfaces for areal and close-range photogrammetry, because the result of the data collection process from the field depended on this.

Figure 6. Laser scanning point cloud dataset of the church (Source: Paten Studio LLC Podgorica).

3.3. Results

The interpretation of the geometric of the church St. Basil of Ostrog in Nikšić data has the goal of creating a three-dimensional model that accurately reflects the spacious character and unique qualities of this historic building. The model is used by architects and engineers during the planning and execution of conservation project, and later for renovation (Figure 7). Ad-

ditionally, the model has been created for documentation purposes to aid in future projects. Modelling and visualization are also critical for interpreting and representing historical and pathologic data. They are also essential for depicting performance data. Moreover, modelling and visualization can be used in education, public awareness, and cultural dissemination, and when combined with XR applications, they can play a significant role in these areas.

Figure 7. a) Architectural 2D drawing of the facade plane (Source: The conservation project of the Church of St. Basil of Ostrog, AVM architect LLC Podgorica); b) gDT facade plane (Source: gDT model, Paten Studio LLC Podgorica).

4. THE CONSERVATION DESIGN PRACTICE

4.1. Common practice in conservation design projects

The initial phase in developing a conservation project involves gathering archival, historical documentation for utilization in the process. This encompasses written materials, as well as graphic and photographic records available in the archives as indicated in Figure 8 of this paper. A crucial aspect of creating a conservation project is the thorough assessment of the building's existing condition, which is then compared to the information obtained from archival sources. Documentation of the current state necessitates the generation of textual reports, photographic records, and, significantly, detailed graphic documentation, including drawings that accurately represent the building's geometry with precise dimensions.

The previous long-standing practice of creating drawings of the existing condition relied on manual surveys. The manual survey is a traditional method where an individual with measuring instruments is in direct contact with the object getting the information. Traditional measuring instruments include a meter, measuring tapes, laser distance meters, protractors, levels, and other helpful equipment. The accuracy of such measurements was susceptible to factors such as human precision, fatigue, and instrument precision, impacting the overall precision of the drawings. These factors affect the accuracy of created drawings of the building (Mrak et al., 2019). The traditional method of surveying usually is not as expensive as a digital survey, but it is still very inaccurate and time-consuming to measure the building geometry by hand. Although laser distance meters can enhance accuracy and flexibility, they still share limitations with manual measurements, and for extensive structures, they may not be economically viable (Khalil et al., 2021).

Figure 8. Workflow of the task

In the process of collecting information on-site, archival drawings are the most helpful, serving as the basis for creating new graphic documentation. After the dimensions are collected and noted on freehand sketches on-site or on a copy of archival drawings, all this documentation is processed by manually creating 2D drawings in one of the architectural programs on the PC (Auto CAD, ArchiCAD etc.). Using photographs and sketches from the field, graphic documentation of the existing condition is generated, which is never completely accurate to the object on-site, neither dimensionally nor geometrically.

In cases where archival drawings are absent, and the structure needs to be surveyed and measured from scratch, the reliance on a geodetic base drawing becomes crucial. However, this method further complicates the task and may not be entirely suitable for the conservation project, especially if the building is large and difficult to access. In such cases, the application of new technologies is accessed to change the way the AEC sector operates. The process of surveying objects using modern technologies, which have proven to be very useful for complex structures, has been accepted for historical objects due to its non-invasive way of documenting (Banfi et al., 2017).

4.2. Conservation requirements

The Regulation on the Detailed Content of the Conservation Project for the Implementation of Conservation Measures on Cultural Heritage regulates the content of the conservation project (“Pravilnik o bližem sadržaju konzervatorskog projekta za sprovođenje konzervatorskih mjera na kulturnom dobru,” n.d.),

stating that each project must include general documentation, textual documentation, numerical documentation, graphic documentation, and photo documentation. Since this work focuses on the creation of the graphic part of the conservation project, we will explain the necessary elements for the graphic documentation as prescribed by this regulation.

The graphic documentation of the project must include drawings of the existing condition of the building, the site plan, floor plans, sections, elevations of the structure, details, and markings of all damages on the building. Additionally, the project must include graphic attachments of the existing condition explaining the planned restoration measures, where it is also necessary to create all corresponding graphic attachments for the building.

For the conservation project of the St. Basil of Ostrog church, there were no drawings of the church in archival documentation which posed a significant challenge for project development. Creating graphic documentation of the existing condition traditionally without any reference material is a substantial task requiring a multifaceted team.

As shown in the modified graph Figure 9, selecting an appropriate recording method depends on the complexity and size of the object to be recorded. Various recording techniques are most efficient in specific situations, underscoring that not all techniques have to be utilized in the same project (Rodríguez-González et al., 2017). To develop the conservation project for the St. Basil of Ostrog church, considering the scale of the structure as well as the complexity of its geometry and the inaccessibility of the roof surfaces, laser scanning and photogrammetry methods were employed.

Figure 9. Survey techniques identified by the complexity and size of the object.

4.3. Applying digitisation in the conservation project

When addressing the restoration of St. Basil's of Ostrog church in Nikšić, it proved most effective to tailor the strategy by aligning the desired outcomes with the capabilities of the digital twin concerning its functionalities during the maintenance phase (Figure 10).

This alignment was defined following the guidelines outlined in ISO 22,263:2008 ("International Standard. 2008. 'ISO Standard, ISO 22263: 2008-01: Organization of Information about Construction Works – Framework for Management of Project Information'", 2008), which delineates the comprehensive process of conserving built cultural heritage.

FUNCTIONALITY	APPLIED		DOCUMENTATION DATA OF HERITAGE BUILDING
	YES	NO	
survey/measurement accuracy	●		Geometry
as-built survey	●		Geometry
3D visualisation	●		Geometry/Pathology
damage/deterioration mapping	●		Pathology
data management	●		History/Geometry/Pathology/Performance
digital fruition	●		History/Geometry/Pathology/Performance
digital reconstruction		●	Geometry
documentation	●		History/Geometry/Pathology/Performance
energy/thermal analysis		●	Performance
indoor environment control		●	Performance
monitoring, performance measurements		●	Performance
people flow control		●	Performance
repair/rehabilitation/restoration planning and execution	●		History/Geom./Pathol./Perform. Conserv. project
structural modelling and analysis		●	Geometry/Pathology
structural health monitoring	●		Geometry/Pathology

Figure 10. Applied in project according to Vuoto A. (2023) (Vuoto, Funari, and Lourenço 2023)

4.4. Demonstration and discussion

The study introduces a conservation project that outlines the process from archival research to on-site reconnaissance, encompassing all essential surveys, measurements and analyses required for project development. To better understand the steps involved in creating a conservation project, they are divided into four phases:

1. Creation of the gDT of St. Basil of Ostrog church (Figure 11)

2. Creation of accurate architectural drawings based on gDT (Figure 12)
3. Analysis of material and structural pathology: gable deterioration, façade closing elements, façade surfaces and ornaments, cornices etc. (Figure 13)
4. Analysis of performances: moisture mapping /water penetration (Figure 14).

The 1st stage is placed on the utilization of photogrammetry and laser scanning, along with the crea-

tion of a gDT to facilitate the documentation of the existing condition and the analysis of the object. The model creation included visualizing the object in 360 degrees at high resolution, along with frontal plans representations of all facades and the roof plan. This

material served architects throughout the entire project development process, and upon completion, it remains as a crucial part of the documentation of the structure, providing utility for future reference.

Figure 11. Views of the current condition exported from the gDT of St. Basil of Ostrog church (Source: gDT model, Paten Studio LLC Podgorica)

2nd stage -The absence of archival drawings, the overall dimensions of the structure, and the inaccessibility of certain parts of the building influenced the decision to create a gDT for the documentation of the

existing condition of the church of St. Basil of Ostrog. Integration of the gDT in the conservation practice has been established for some time now in the world, but in Montenegro, this is one of the first projects that

integrates gDT in this particular way into the creation process of conservation project.

The gDT produced a geometrically and metrically accurate model of the church, which was employed in generating architectural drawings of the structure. This approach has considerably sped up the process of producing drawings for the existing condition

compared to the traditional on-site measurement method, resulting in drawings characterized by high levels of detail and precision. The created model provided all the necessary information for the development of accurate architectural drawings of the existing condition.

Figure 12. Accurate architectural drawings created based on the data from the gDT model (Source: The conservation project of the Church of St. Basil of Ostrog, AVM architect LLC Podgorica).

In the 3rd stage of the study, it's noteworthy that, until now, no research has delved into the St. Basil of Ostrog church, resulting in this analysis being crucial

for acquiring new insights into its structural composition, material pathology, and current conservation status. The generated gDT for this church played a

key role in defining material pathologies, encompassing stone, wood, and metal. The detail and precision of the digital twin have proven highly beneficial, especially in analyzing and documenting material deterioration, particularly in inaccessible parts of the structure. Accurate documentation of material pathology is very important for later decision-making in proposed interventions across different scenarios.

Additionally, presenting the object as a comprehensive rendered 3D model in 360 degrees, facilitated the examination of all parts of the church at any given stage throughout the project development. The 3D model was uploaded to the online platform 3dvirtualheritage.me which uses functionalities of Nira platform [<https://www.nirafinance.com/>], providing architects with the capability to view the entire church and analyze structural and material pathologies at any given time. This digital tool proved instrumental in enhancing accessibility and insight into the church's condition during the entirety of the project.

Considering the project requirements and the presented issues by the owner regarding the structure, an on-site inspection and analysis of the gDT model were conducted to analyze the deterioration and pathology of the structure and materials. On the architectural drawings of the object, all problematic segments and visible damages were initially marked. The

purpose is to address issues related to deterioration and to demonstrate the optimal method for conservation measures and preventing its recurrence in the future. The precision of the gDT facilitated the easier documentation of damages on the structure and materials, subsequently expediting the process of mapping and explaining specific damages in the project. Table III illustrates the mapping of damages on the drawing from the project. Each color represents a specific type of damage and elaborates on the conservation treatment approach to address the issue within the project. Marked points on the drawings of structure and material pathology, primarily include changes to the stone elements of the facade, damage to the wooden joinery, as well as damage to the gutters and the metal roof covering. This project processed the following damages: removal of vegetation, cleaning, repairs, and hydrophobization of stone elements (stairs, windows, ornaments), removal of recent coatings on the facade, repair of cracks in the stone, reconstruction of damaged facade ornaments, replacement of gutters, repair of tiles on the roof covering, replacement of facade joinery, conservation of both crosses on the roof, repair, and cleaning of the clock.

Figure 13. Accurate architectural drawing with pathology analysis: gable deterioration, façade closing elements, façade surfaces and ornaments, cornices etc. marked and described in the project documentation (Source: The conservation project of the Church of St. Basil of Ostrog, AVM architect LLC Podgorica).

The final, 4th section, unveils the performances of the main problem for this structure – moisture/water penetration. In this specific case, the church's roof covering exhibited the most significant damage, leading to moisture infiltration inside the structure. These damages were not visible from the ground level around the church. In their discovery, the gDT 3D model proved helpful, allowing us to examine the roof surfaces and identify the root cause of the problem. Problematic spots turn out to be the junctions of the roof covering and the façade are the points of water penetration into the building. This detail of the

building shows the cause of the degradation inside the church and the specific position on the roof where the damage allows water penetration inside. The ability to view the object in 360 degrees enabled accelerated problem identification. In the table IV present a moisture penetration issue, which was observed within the interior of the building, and the problem was clarified through the gDT which resulted in the creation of conservation measures in the early problem identification phase.

A problematic spot on the roof with the unprofessional attempt to seal junctions resulted the water penetration inside the object causing interior moisture damage

A problematic spot on the roof with the unprofessional attempt to seal junctions and the poor edge details of the roof covering resulted the water penetration inside the object causing interior moisture damage

The damaged gutters fail to drain water properly, causing it to overflow down the stone facade, resulting in stone causing façade stone damage from moisture

Figure 14. Analysis of performances: moisture/water penetration showing cause a, c, e (Source: gDT model, Paten Studio LLC Podgorica) and consequence of the damage b, d (Photo credit: Ražnatović, N.) and f (Source: gDT model, Paten Studio LLC Podgorica).

5. CONCLUSION

The collected data during the research indicate that the subject church was built in the late 19th century, and since then, there have been no detailed architectural drawings of the structure available in the archives of Montenegro. The application of gDT creation technologies, such as photogrammetry and laser scanning, in the conservation project for the Church of St. Basil of Ostrog has produced remarkable results in this phase by creating significant documentation material of the church for preventive measures.

These advanced methods have significantly enhanced the efficiency and precision of the project,

marking a substantial departure from traditional conservation practices. This innovative method in Montenegro's conservation practices not only expedited the creation of accurate architectural drawings but also established a precedent for the incorporation of advanced technologies in conservation initiatives. The gDT's proficiency in capturing material pathologies in challenging locations significantly influenced decision-making for proposed interventions, showcasing the versatility and effectiveness of these technologies. The adaptability, efficiency, and enduring utility of these technologies underscore their transformative potential in preserving cultural heritage.

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